

Oil Industries in Ballari and Vijayanagara Districts Inscriptions

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Abstract:

Inscriptions from the Ballari and Vijayanagara districts depict a variety of industrial activities. Inscriptional sources can be used to determine that industries have been in this area since ancient times because the geographical environment is also quite rich. Oil manufacturing was historically a key industry among those that did exist. The Ballari and Vijayanagara districts' inscriptions describe the Gana (oil-making industry) as a clan craft. In light of the foregoing, this article uses an inscription framework to examine the development of the oil manufacturing industries in the Ballari and Vijayanagara districts and the taxation system, production, and commerce.

Keywords: Gana, Ganiga, Oil Industries, Inscriptions, Production, Trading Activities, Taxation, Ballari, Vijayanagara.

Introduction:

The Ballari and Vijayanagar districts have had manufacturing businesses for centuries. The mass industry is the manufacturing sector activity that appears most frequently in inscriptions from these two districts. Since ancient times, oil-producing operations have been observed in this setting. In the temple and other religious activities of the society, oil is very significant. This research paper's present goal is to examine the oil industry in the Inscriptions by focusing on the Inscriptions of these two regions. From the Mauryan to

the Paleyagaras periods are represented in inscriptions from the Ballari and Vijayanagara districts. In this research article, the reference to the oil business/industries in a total of 635 inscriptions that have been found so far has been identified and evaluated.

Etymology of Gana and Ganiga:

The Kannada dictionary defines Gana as an apparatus for extracting juice or oil from sugarcane. One who extracts oil and sells it for a living is referred to as a Ganiga. One who prepares oil with Gana is known as a Ganiga, as is the entire oil-making sector. Inscriptions refer to Telligars as Ganigas or oil manufacturers.

Oil Industries in Ballari District Inscriptions:

An inscription with the date 27.05.1210 is attached to the wall of the Kuditini Kumaraswamy temple in the Ballari district and mentions Gana. A house, some land, and an oil mill for a perpetual lamp were left as a donation to Lord Nageshwar by the eight crore followers of Lord Vishnukaradeva and Banajiga who met as a Mahasabha. In this inscription there is a reference to “Biḷukuṇṭeya dāriya teṅka brahmacāri mukhyasthāna dayduvargaṅgaḍēvara nandādivigege biṭṭa gāṇa”.¹

Oil Industries in Vijayanagara District Inscriptions:

In an inscription dated 16.07.1146 in front of the Math of Uluvatti village in Hagaribommanahalli taluk, there is a reference to giving oil to God's lamp (Nandadeepa). During the reign of Kadamba Machideva Kogali-500, Ajjagamunda, son of Nalprabhu Singagamunda of Uyyalvatti, granted land to his family as merit. On that occasion, the Telligars (Miners) there gave oil to the lamp (Nandadeepa) of God. This inscription also says “(a)llyia telligaru śrīrāmēsvradēvaranandā(dī)vigege soliga eṇṇeyam koṭṭaru”.²

An inscription dated 08.01.1201 on a thole in the temple of Kuruvatti village of Hadagali taluk mentions payment for oil for the lamp (Nandadeepa) of Yahuvamalleswara temple. It is said that the officials and the entire village left this donation to Rajaguru Lokabharanadev. This inscription also says “samasta nāyakarum śrī maddakṣiṇa vāraṇāsi kuruvattiya yāhuvamallēśvara soḍareṇṇege ūroḷagaṇa purada kabbilara billahaṇavondum”.³

A crumbling inscription on an inscription near the main entrance of the Somalingeshwar temple in Mailara village of Hadagali taluk mentions that Kalidasa, the son of Barmmadevaiah, donated another piece of land to the lamp (for Nandadeepa) of the original deity.⁴

In an inscription dated 14.10.1225 on the pillar in Kaisale of Narasimhaswamy temple in Rangapur village of Hadagali taluk, there is a mention that a Dandanayaka named Polalpa gave a house and an oil gana to the lamp (Nandadeepa) of Narasimhadev in the presence of 200 Mahajanas of Mongola. The inscription says “pōlālva daṇḍanāyakaru śrīmanumahāgrahāraṁ māṅḷada śrīnarasinhyadēvara nandādīvigege alliyūraḍeyapramukhavaśēṣa mahājanavinnorvvarṁ'mukhyavāgi ghais'sagēriya modalu teṅkavāgila mane gāṇaṁ sahita sarbbābādhe parihāravāgi koṭṭaru".⁵

An inscription on the eastern face of the right pillar of the Navaranga of the Rameswara temple in Rangapur village of Hadagali taluk mentions the offering of Gadyana for oil. Jakkatasa, son of Nacharasa of Magula, gives two verses to Somaiya, son of Ramisetty, for the oil of Ramanathadeva's lamp. The inscription says that “māḷada nācarsara maga jakkarsaru rāmanātha dēvara dīptige māneṅṅeya naḍasuvantāgi telliga rāmisettiya maga sōmayyaṅge hokkalu gaḍanāgi koṭṭa ga 2 yi dharmava ninnūvaru pālisuvaru śrī rāmanātha".⁶

An inscription dated 25.12.1121 in front of the Dabbagudi of Sogi village mentions the donation of ghee for the food of Brahmins.⁷

Gana is mentioned in an inscription dated 25.06.1165 at Badageramatti Dinne of Uchchandidurga village in Harappanahalli taluk. The inscription said “golamānavatiruva'aṅgaḍiyanitarilu soṭige bhattavanettuvuru nandādīvigege maṇa. Risahita naḍava gāṇa(kke) ceṭṭanahallīya ceṭṭanakeriya baḍagaṇa kōḍiyim baḍagaṇa ciṅkama".⁸

An inscription dated 24.12.1044 near Kalleshwar temple in Sattur village of Harappanahalli taluk mentions the donation of Gana to Lamp (Nandadeepa).⁹

An inscription dated 11.01.1050 near Chirastihalli Sankaralingaswamy temple in Harappanahalli taluk mentions the donation of Gana. The inscription mentions “panneraḍu maneyanelasaṇavettugāṇa 1 kaigāṇa".¹⁰

Production and Trading Activities:

In Gana, oil was typically prepared using customary techniques. The traditional procedure in this case can be understood as the process of producing oil employing a Bull. Sometimes Hand Gana and Metu Gana prepared the oil. Oil was produced from grains like sesame, peanuts, and others. It can be said that the oil prepared from Gana was used for cooking, Lamps in the temple and for other medicinal purposes.

The majority of sales efforts were done through Ganas and Temples. Gana used to receive donations for its lamp from visitors to the temples. Donors would be responsible for the quantity's cost. Inscriptions from the Ballari and Vijayanagar districts occasionally make mention of donations of land to the Ganas. Also worth mentioning is that Gana was left as a gift for the Brahmins' meals.

Taxation:

Taxes named Ganadere, Ganasunka, and Ganaya were levied on oil manufacturing industries. The tax should have been fixed by measuring the oil produced in gauges. Oil ingredients were measured by gauges like Ganavari Ganamprati Mana-1. Valla, Mana, Sollige, Ardha Sollige, Suttuga, Solasa, Dala, Hase, and Palige Khanduga were other measurements used.¹¹

Conclusion:

Nowadays traditional oil-making methods are disappearing. People of those days used to prepare pure oil in their own way, without any sophisticated equipment. However, even with all the modern equipment at present, oil industries produce pure oil very rarely. The oil makers/miners of that period used to supply oil to God's lamps in the temples. They formed their association and participated in social and religious activities like others. The area where he lives is known as Ganadokkalu, Ganadaravathokalu, Telligarayvathokalu.

Endnotes:

1. Devarakondareddy (Ed.), 1999, Kannada University Epigraphical Series-I, Bellary District, p.38.
2. Ibid p.260.
3. Ibid p.323.
4. Ibid p.331.
5. Ibid p.400.
6. Ibid p.402.
7. Ibid p.443.
8. Ibid p.462.
9. Ibid p.484-485.
10. Ibid p.509.
11. Vasudev Badiger, 2012, Ballari Parisarada Samskrutika Paramapare, p.248.

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